

Peer assessment in the large class context: instructor reflections, student perceptions, feedback quality, and the impact of anonymity

Darina Scully¹, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6076-717X>

Ernesto Panadero¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0859-3616>

Conor Scully² <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2010-6624>

¹ Centre for Assessment Research, Policy & Practice in Education (CARPE), Institute of Education, Dublin City University

² Institute of Education, Dublin City University

Abstract

A mid-semester peer assessment (PA) was implemented in two iterations of a large undergraduate psychology module ($n = 102$ and 107 students respectively). Students completed a written assignment, evaluated the work of a peer (providing a grade alongside rubric-assisted and open-ended written feedback), and revised their own work based on the feedback they received. Half engaged in the process anonymously. A subset of students across both cohorts completed pre- and post- questionnaires measuring beliefs about PA and emotional states. Changes in these variables after participating in the PA were measured, and the impact of anonymity was investigated. Feedback quality was also analysed using an adapted coding scheme. Students' social concerns about PA decreased after participating, and anonymity did not impact on their experience of the process. Feedback quality was low. The instructors' reflections on the process and implications for practice are discussed, placing particular emphasis on the large class context.

Keywords: *Peer assessment; feedback, large classes, social processes, emotions, anonymity (maximum 6).*

1. Introduction

Feedback remains one of the most persistent pedagogical challenges in large higher education classes, where tensions are well documented between students' desire for greater personalization and specificity, and instructors' concerns regarding practical constraints (e.g., Henderson et al., 2019). Peer assessment (PA) represents a promising pedagogy for enhancing feedback practices in large class contexts, as it reduces reliance on instructor commentary and affords students the opportunity to actively engage with assessment criteria and develop their capacity for evaluative judgement, which aligns well with contemporary conceptualizations of feedback as an active, dialogic process (Winstone & Carless, 2020). Well-designed PA may also help address other frequently documented concerns associated with large-class teaching, such as low student-student interaction, poor engagement and passivity (Black et al., 2021, Mulryan-Kyne, 2010).

PA is a complex activity, however, involving not just cognitive, but also social and interpersonal processes (Panadero et al., 2023). Consequently, a thorough understanding of the conditions under which it is most effective is still developing (Fleckney et al., 2024). This paper provides an account of a PA implementation in a large class context in a higher education institution in Ireland, with reflections on challenges encountered and key learnings. It also reports on an experimental investigation of the impact of anonymity on students' perceptions of the PA, their emotions during the process, and the quality of the feedback they provided.

2. Description of the Teaching and Learning Context

The PA was implemented in two successive offerings of the same undergraduate NFQ Level 8, five ECTS modules in Spring 2024 ($n = 107$ students) and Spring 2025 ($n = 102$ students). The module, 'Psychology of Adolescence', introduces students to both historical and contemporary theories of adolescent development and aims to enhance their understanding of the biological, cognitive and psychosocial transitions of this period, and the practical applications of this knowledge. It is delivered through ten plenary lectures, supplemented by four smaller group tutorials ($n = 10-15$ students) facilitated by a teaching assistant. Students taking the module are all enrolled in a Bachelor of Arts (Joint Honours) programme, studying Human Development – an interdisciplinary subject drawing on psychology, sociology and philosophy – alongside one additional subject. This context exposes them to a diverse range of perspectives which has the potential to enrich class discussions, however, it also presents a challenge for the instructor, as it limits the depth with which any single discipline can be explored. The programme is situated within a faculty of education, and although these students pursue a variety of career paths, a significant proportion typically aspire to progress to postgraduate teacher education

programmes, creating a heightened emphasis on applied learning. Finally, the class size is large, and the instructor had been experiencing many of the challenges associated with large class teaching, such as low student engagement and dwindling attendance throughout the semester (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010) in the years leading up to the introduction of the PA.

Up to 2023, the module was assessed solely via an end-of-term essay. Although personalized written feedback was provided, this was extremely onerous for the instructor and its timing at the end of the semester limited its pedagogical value. Students were also disinclined to engage deeply with the content over the course of the semester, often completing the essay in the final weeks, resulting in limited critical reflection and predominantly surface-level learning. Again, this reflects a commonly encountered difficulty in the large class context (Maringe & Sing, 2014). A mid-semester PA was introduced to encourage earlier and deeper engagement with the course content, to activate students as learning resources for one another, and to provide them with the opportunity to develop their evaluative judgement. For students interested in pursuing careers in education, it also offered additional applied benefits by providing first-hand experience of evaluating work and giving constructive feedback.

3. Literature Review

PA refers to any situation where students grade or provide feedback on each other's work. It has been associated with increased academic performance across a variety of settings (Double et al., 2020), but it may be particularly suited to higher education (HE) contexts, where students' metacognitive skills are more developed (Veenman et al., 2006), and specifically, large classes, where the challenge of feedback is most acute (Maringe & Sing, 2014).

The precise way in which PA is implemented can vary considerably. For example, it may be carried out for formative or summative purposes, it may supplement teacher assessment or substitute it completely, it may occur once or several times, and it may be anonymous or non-anonymous (see Alqassab et al., 2023 for a comprehensive review of various PA design elements). Each of these variations may impact on how the process is experienced by students, on how they engage with it, and in turn, how effective it is in terms of promoting learning. For instance, evidence suggests that anonymity may enhance students' perceptions of the learning value of PA and also result in more critical feedback, although the number of studies focusing on this is limited and the use of true experimental design is rare (Panadero & Alqassab, 2019).

Previous research in the Irish HE context has found that students hold relatively negative attitudes towards PA (McGarrigle, 2013), and tend to focus on whether their peers' judgements can be considered accurate or fair, giving limited consideration to the potential

educational value of the process (Egan & Costello, 2016, McGarr & Clifford 2013). These findings were, at the time, interpreted as a reflection of the prevailing exam-dominant culture in Ireland. The assessment landscape, however, has since evolved considerably, both nationally, with assessment reforms at second level and globally, with a growing interest in the diversification of assessment methods in HE, intensified by the pivot to online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic and the emergence of generative AI (Corbin et al., 2025). In light of these shifts, it is possible that Irish HE students may now be more open to the concept of PA and its potential benefits – and particularly in large classes where they experience infrequent opportunities to engage in feedback dialogue (Maringe & Sing, 2014).

In light of the above, there is a lot to be learned from detailed descriptions of specific PA implementations, instructors' professional reflections on the process, and targeted empirical investigations of the impact of various contextual factors on the process and outcomes of PA.

4. Empirical Methodology/Data

Students were asked to complete and submit a short (750 word) critical analysis of the portrayal of adolescence in a media source of their choosing in week 4 of the semester. In line with best practice recommendations (Taylor et al., 2024), a rubric was shared with students from the outset to ensure clarity regarding expectations. After the initial task has been completed, the instructor dedicated approximately 30 minutes of scheduled class time to introducing the concept of PA and how to approach it. This included providing explicit guidance on how to apply the rubric criteria, sharing illustrative examples of sample work aligned with various level descriptors, and outlining the characteristics of effective feedback. Particular emphasis was placed on this training aspect in light of meta-analytic evidence suggesting that is the most significant factor influencing the effectiveness of PA (Li et al., 2020), and more generally, calls for a greater emphasis on the development of students' feedback literacy (Molloy et al., 2020).

The PA itself took place over the course of two successive class sessions. Students were asked to bring their laptops to class on both occasions. In the first session, each student received an email containing the work of one of their peers. In addition to assessing the work in line with the rubric and assigning a grade, students were encouraged to leave open-ended feedback comments. At the end of the session, students submitted the grades, feedback and completed rubric to the course platform. In the second session, students received an email containing the grades, completed rubric and feedback provided by their peers and were given the opportunity to revise their original piece of work. The grades exchanged during the PA did not contribute to the overall module grade, rather, meaningful

participation in the process was weighted at 10%. This approach was used in order to strike a balance between motivating students to engage with the process and facilitating honest and authentic PA.

As the PA was part of the module coursework, all students across both cohorts completed it. Separately, the students were also invited to participate in a research study of the process. Those who consented to participate ($n = 89$) completed a questionnaire prior to completing the PA. Items adapted from an instrument developed by Rotsaert et al. (2017) were used to measure attitudes and beliefs about PA, specifically: Perceived Value (*e.g.* “assessing my peer’s work will be useful”), Trust in Own and Peer’s Evaluative Capabilities (*e.g.* “I have the necessary skills to accurately assess my peer’s work”), Social Concerns (*e.g.* “During the PA, I will be reluctant to give negative feedback because of the possible reaction of my peer”), Psychological Safety (*e.g.* “I can share my opinion in this group without hesitation”) and the Importance of Anonymity (*e.g.* “During PA, I think it is important that your anonymity as an assessor is guaranteed”). The Positive and Negative Affect Scale (PANAS; Watson et al., 1988) was also used to measure the extent to which participants typically experienced various emotions when completing academic work. Student numbers were collected to enable linkage of questionnaire responses with the feedback provided during the PA. However, once the linkage was complete, the dataset was fully anonymised for analysis.

All participants were randomly assigned to either an anonymous or non-anonymous PA condition. These sessions were held in separate rooms to prevent cross-contamination, with a teaching assistant facilitating one of the sessions. In the anonymous condition, individuals’ names and student numbers were redacted from the submitted documents and ‘author information’ was removed using the document inspector function on Microsoft Word before the work was assigned to a peer assessor. In the non-anonymous condition, names and student numbers were retained, and students were explicitly instructed to include their name as the assessor when completing the rubric.

Following the PA, participants completed another questionnaire measuring the same attitudes and emotions from a post-participation perspective, and inviting their open-ended reflections on the process. Changes in attitudes and emotions were analysed, and the moderating impact of anonymity on these trajectories was investigated using a series of mixed factorial ANOVAs. The feedback provided by participants during the PA was also analysed, drawing on elements of Van den Berg et al. (2006)’s peer feedback coding scheme, and Hattie and Timperley (2007)’s model of feedback. Specifically, comments were coded according to their function (analysis, revision, evaluation with explanation, evaluation without explanation), the aspect of the work to which they applied (content, structure or style), and the level of cognitive engagement they invited (task, process or self-regulation).

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Participation in the PA had no impact on Perceived Value, Trust or Psychological Safety. Social Concerns, however, decreased significantly from pre- ($m = 3.20, sd = .91$) to post-participation ($m = 2.82, sd = 1.09$), with a significant main effect of time $F(1, 42) = 6.36, p = .016, \eta^2 = .13$ collapsed across anonymity conditions. Self-reported Positive Affect during the PA was comparable to typical levels of Positive Affect experienced during academic work across both conditions, whilst Negative Affect was significantly lower, $F(1, 39) = 36.7, p < .001, \eta^2 = .49$. With respect to Importance of Anonymity, a significant time x condition interaction was observed, $F(1, 29) = 5.27, p = .029, \eta^2 = .15$. Follow-up analyses indicated that participants who experienced anonymous PA placed a higher value on anonymity post-participation, whereas students who experienced non-anonymous PA showed no significant change (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Changes in mean ratings for Importance of Anonymity in PA from pre- to post- participation

Students' open-ended comments revealed predominantly positive experiences of the process, with many articulating enjoyment, learning benefits, and the development of transferrable professional skills ("It made understanding the rubric far easier"... "it gave us a look at how another student might approach a question differently to yourself"... "it's really quick and easy to do and we can already see ourselves as teachers").

Preliminary analyses of the peer feedback revealed the quality to be relatively low. Specifically, many students provided evaluative comments, but few elaborated on these, offered suggested revisions or posed questions to encourage reflection. One student commented on this limitation, but simultaneously noted that it could be improved through

further engagement with PA (“Unfortunately the feedback I received was limited and the rubric form wasn’t highlighted correctly. I suppose this is simply a fact of students conducting an exercise like this for the first time... if this were a more regular activity I expect it would be much smoother”).

5. Reflections on and Implications for Practice

For practitioners who may be interested in implementing PA in large class contexts, this experience offers a number of insights. First, the empirical findings suggest that for students, the process is not as uncomfortable as some expect it to be. Simply engaging in PA firsthand seems to alleviate social concerns, furthermore, the emotions experienced during the process appear comparable to those typically experienced during academic work. This is encouraging in a large class context, where many students do not know each other personally (Gibbs, 1992) and therefore may feel more wary about the process of evaluating or being evaluated by a classmate.

From the instructor’s perspective, the PA offered a refreshing change from the previous assessment arrangements. As Mulryan-Kyan (2010, p. 182) noted, changes to longstanding teaching, learning and assessment approaches can be associated with “discomfort and anxiety” due to the inherent risks (*e.g.*, students may not engage with the new approach, the instructor may feel a loss of control) and additional time demands involved. This was undoubtedly a feature of this experience. However, benefits became apparent almost immediately. Students began engaging meaningfully with the course content earlier in the semester, as evidenced by in-class questions and email communication. There was also a noticeable improvement in attendance in the weeks immediately prior to and after the PA sessions. This is especially encouraging, given that low student engagement and attendance are recognized as two of the most prominent challenges associated with the large class context (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010).

The in-class nature of the PA also worked well. Although this was intended primarily to facilitate controlled conditions for the research, on reflection, it also supported a more equitable learning environment by ensuring all students had structured and consistent time to engage with the task. It may also have helped reduce opportunities for the use of generative AI during the feedback process. As the feedback was written rather than oral, however, and as some students did not know the identity of their partner, the extent to which the process could be considered truly dialogical (Winstone & Carless, 2020) was limited. Non-anonymous PA would be required to support this, as it provides the possibility of students having the opportunity to “explain or defend ideas” to their assessor, and develop transferrable communication skills (Lynch & Pappas, 2017). As previous findings about the impact of anonymity on PA have been mixed, neither approach was favoured in

this instance, rather, this element was incorporated into the study design. Strikingly, anonymity had no impact on students' social and emotional experiences of the PA process, or on their perceptions of its value. Experiencing anonymous PA appeared only to lead to the belief that anonymity in PA is important. Incidentally, the process of de-identifying students' submissions was also time-consuming for the instructor. As anonymity appears not to have a socio-emotional impact for students, and as it removes the possibility of engaging in feedback dialogue, non-anonymous arrangements may be preferable. However, it is also important to note that this PA was low-stakes and formative in nature, and different patterns may emerge in cases whereby the peer-assigned grades are used in the calculation of the module grade (Panadero & Alqassab, 2019).

The pedagogical quality of the peer feedback provided was relatively low, despite the instructor providing explicit guidance to this end, which calls into question the extent to which PA can be considered to act as a substitute for what an instructor might provide. This could be interpreted as a discouraging finding, as this is often assumed to be one of the main advantages of the approach in the large class context. That said, some have argued that PA provides the most benefits for students not through the feedback they receive, but through the process of assessing their peer's work (Patchan & Schunn, 2015). Indeed, it is this *feedback provider* role that exposes them to alternative perspectives and requires them to engage with the performance criteria, developing their sense of what constitutes 'good work', which can in turn be applied to their own future work. Students' open-ended reflections revealed that they perceived learning value in both the provider and the recipient roles, which is consistent with recent findings suggesting that both roles lead to similar performance gains over time (Zamorano et al., 2026). It is also interesting that one student who was dissatisfied with the feedback they received still recognised the value of PA, and suggested that this could be improved through multiple iterations of the process.

Overall, these findings suggest that PA can be safely implemented in large classes, creating opportunities for engagement without undue social or emotional strain, and that providing anonymous conditions may not be necessary. Furthermore, they reveal that students require ongoing support in terms of developing feedback literacy. More generally, the study demonstrates the depth of insight that can be gleaned by combining practitioner insights with rigorous research design in large class settings, and that although the ethical and procedural challenges of such inquiry can be substantial, they are worth navigating.

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